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Bibliotheca Eugeniiana Digital— Unveiling and Visualizing the Treasures of Prince Eugene of Savoy’s Library

Eva Mayr¹[0000–0001–8402–5990], Annerose Tartler²[0009–0009–4141–4270],
Florian Windhager¹[0000–0002–5170–2243], Michael Smuc³,
Johannes Liem¹[0000–0001–8696–0245], Max Kaiser²[0000–0002–4964–4793],
Monika Kiegler-Griensteidl², and Simon Mayer²[0009–0008–3322–5130]

¹ University for Continuing Education, Krems, AT

`firstname.lastname@donau-uni.ac.at`

<https://www.donau-uni.ac.at/cctc/>

² Austrian National Library, Vienna, AT

`firstname.lastname@onb.ac.at`

<https://www.onb.ac.at/en>

³ MindFactor IT Solutions eU

`office@mindfactor.at`

<https://www.mindfactor.at>

Abstract. The Bibliotheca Eugeniiana is deemed one of the most important Baroque book collections worldwide. After the death of Eugene of Savoy and its acquisition by the Austrian National Library, it became integrated into the overall collection—but without a systematic identifier in the library catalog. The project *Bibliotheca Eugeniiana Digital* aims to make this historical collection accessible again for research and open exploration. Starting from a historical handwritten catalog and digital scans of the Austrian National Library, this project applies techniques from the Digital Humanities (HTR, machine learning) to digitize the historic catalog, to identify book covers with the historical supralibros of Prince Eugene of Savoy, and to match entries between the historical and the modern catalog. The results are made accessible in a digital edition for future research. Additionally, a collection visualization enables the visual analysis of the books’ current arrangement in the Austrian National Library, their categorical classification, and their temporal and regional origins. The visual interface also enables exploration by the wider public and aims to increase awareness of this UNESCO Memory of Austria heritage collection.

Keywords: Historical Book Collection · Digital Edition · Machine Learning · HTR · Collection visualization.

1 Introduction

Prince Eugene of Savoy (1663–1736) was one of Europe’s most successful military commanders of his time. Apart from his victories on the battlefield and his diplomatic successes, Prince Eugene cultivated a profound appreciation for the arts,

sciences, and humanities, amassing a collection of approximately 15,000 printed books and 2,400 manuscripts that document the intellectual spirit of his era. The so-called *Bibliotheca Eugeniiana* is an important instantiation of the general body of knowledge during the 17th and 18th centuries and spans from history to theology, literature, philosophy, and the natural sciences, as documented in two multi-volume handwritten catalogs. As such, UNESCO acknowledged it to be part of the “Memory of Austria” heritage. After Eugene’s death, the collection was sold to the Habsburgs and transferred into the new State Hall for the Imperial Library (the predecessor of the Austrian National Library, ONB) in 1738.

Yet, despite its historic importance, little is known about the size, composition, and current status of the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana within the ONB [6]. Descriptions of the library [13,16] usually refer to a set of well-documented objects, like the famous Tabula Peutingeriana⁴, but information about the composition of the collection in its entirety is limited, as its sheer size and missing documentation has been an obstacle for a full reconstruction.

In this paper, we introduce the project *Bibliotheca Eugeniiana Digital* (BED)⁵, which uses tools and methods from the Digital Humanities, Machine Learning, and Data Science for a systematic reconstruction of this historical library collection. Large-scale digitization, algorithmically supported workflows, and the application of artificial intelligence offer new possibilities to digitally reconstruct this important library. In this paper, we describe the creation of a digital edition by combining information from the handwritten catalog, images of the supra-libros bindings, and the modern catalog (section 2) and the development of a visualization-based interface for the exploration of the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana (section 3), before we discuss implications of our project for digital library research and practice (section 4).

2 From a Handwritten Catalog to a Digital Edition

When the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana was transferred into the new State Hall for the Imperial Library in 1738, the books received library signatures starting with ‘BE’ for ‘Bibliotheca Eugeniiana’. Over the course of centuries, several books from Bibliotheca Eugeniiana were moved to other collections of ONB (and also to the Albertina Museum’s graphic collection), while books of other provenances have been added to the shelves in the State Hall, also receiving a ‘BE’ signature. Thereby, the original shelfmark “BE” became an indicator for a book’s placement in the center of the State Hall, but lost its validity as an indicator for historical provenance. Since no new systematic indicator for the collection has been introduced to the catalog since then, other sources and approaches had to be considered to reconstruct the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana.

One such source is a five-volume handwritten catalog [2], which contains three thematically arranged volumes (which presumably follow a taxonomy by

⁴ <https://onb.digital/result/10002029>

⁵ <https://labs.onb.ac.at/bed/>

Leibniz [19]) and two alphabetically organized volumes. As no printed catalog of the library exists [1], the handwritten catalog is the only resource for research on this book collection⁶ but it is also difficult to access [6]. Therefore, an important aim of this project was the digitization and processing of this handwritten catalog to create a digital edition, which can be linked to the modern library catalog (see section 2.1).

Another source for the digital reconstruction of the Bibliotheca Eugeniana are the bindings of its books: Eugene had a substantial part of his books equipped with supralibros bindings in three different colors (allegedly corresponding to taxonomic supercategories), which thus provide a valid indicator for provenance identification. We apply Machine Learning techniques [10] to ONB's digitized historic book collection to recognize and identify both the color of the books' bindings and the presence of Eugene's coats of arms on these bindings (see section 2.2).

2.1 Digitizing the Handwritten Catalog

Fig. 1. Transcription of a page from the handwritten catalog within Transkribus with highlighting of specific elements.

Applying automated handwritten text recognition, we digitized the thematically arranged part of the Bibliotheca Eugeniana's handwritten collection catalog [2,

⁶ Together with another closely related three-volume handwritten catalog (Cod. 13963–13966).

Vol. 1–3] using the HTR platform Transkribus [3]. Based on the best-performing pre-existing model⁷, we trained our own HTR transcription model with a randomly selected training set (41 pages with a total of almost 7,000 words, of which approx. 15% were used as validation set) and got a resulting model with approx. 3.70% word error rate⁸. This model was subsequently applied to all 1500 catalog pages. To minimize the frequency of errors, in particular for occasionally occurring deviating scribal hands (like additions in between lines), the digitized texts were corrected manually.

Inside the Transkribus client, only tags directly related to the visual image (most often occurrences of other scribal hands, lead pencil, or sanguine) were assigned. After exporting the three files in TEI-XML format, we cleaned them and added source-specific tags such as page number, book format, classification category and sub-category (following the catalog’s taxonomy), and catalog entries. Additionally, we created tags for special text markup: unclear (for text that cannot be read), abbreviation, addition, correction, and strike-through.

In the next step, the individual book entries of the historical catalog are searched for in the modern ONB catalog to obtain an overview of books from Prince Eugene’s Collection that are still in the ONB’s holdings and to create cross-references between the modern library catalog and their associated digitized books and the digital edition. Given the high frequency of abbreviations and inflections in the handwritten catalog, we created a string-matching algorithm, which retrieves the five most similar catalog entries for each entry. The final selection of the most likely entry for each title was done manually.

2.2 Supralibros Analyses

A large number of the volumes in the Bibliotheca Eugenia bear supralibros with three different variants of Prince Eugene’s *coat of arms* on the leather binding (see figure 2). While a manual inspection of all books would be difficult, an algorithmic approach became possible due to the large-scale project ‘Austrian Books Online’ [9,7], during which the vast collections of historical books held in the Austrian National Library have been digitized. So far, more than 600,000 digitized volumes are available for computational analysis, among them nearly all of the Bibliotheca Eugenia’s printed books.

With a machine learning approach (based on [10]), we were able to search for Prince Eugene’s supralibros in the entire digitized historical book holdings of the ONB and thereby assign them to the collection in a data-driven manner. We trained a machine learning algorithm on a subsample (Type A: 200, Type B: 234, Type C: 200, other supralibros: 884) and applied it to the images of 557,084 book covers from the digitized book collection (see [10] for the selection

⁷ Transkribus German handwriting M1 - model 35909, see <https://readcoop.eu/model/transkribus-german-handwriting-m1/>.

⁸ For irregular pages, e.g. with additions in-between lines, performance was slightly worse (approx. 11% word error rate), but as the catalog consists predominantly of regular pages, this error rate seems acceptable.

Fig. 2. Three variants of Prince Eugene’s coat of arms on the bookbindings within the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana (top) and probability histograms from the image classification for each variant (bottom, note the exponential scaling of the y-axis).

procedure). Across all three variants, the algorithm identified 59 false positives and 6,161 true positives, which corresponds to a precision of .991 (see figure 2 for probability distribution).⁹

Given the assumed amount of 15,000 books within the Bibliotheca Eugeniiana, the number of 6,161 identified bindings seems quite low. This can be explained by different factors: (1) There are also bindings without Prince Eugene’s supralibros within the collection (most probably, because Prince Eugene acquired them already bound). (2) Particularly valuable or oversized manuscripts have not been digitized within the Austrian Books Online project and therefore could not be analyzed with this machine-learning approach. (3) At the end of the project also a fourth variant of Eugene’s coat of arms has been found on one of the books—which has not been taken into account for this analysis, yet.

Next to Prince Eugene’s specific supralibros, the bindings’ *leather color* is of interest: It was assumed that it correlates with a book’s wider topic—dark blue for Theology and Law, dark red for History and Poetry, and yellow for Natural Sciences [16, p.25], but this association has also been questioned recently [13, p.194]. Therefore, we modified the machine learning algorithm to identify the leather color of all books with Prince Eugene’s supralibros and again trained it

⁹ Due to their high number, we could not analyze the false negatives as well within this project. See [10] for a discussion of false negatives.

with a sub-sample (blue: 136, yellow: 410, and red: 466 images). The precision of the final resulting algorithm was .99. From the overall sample, 4,325 were identified as red, 1,697 as yellow, and 139 as blue. The resulting sets of books can now be analyzed regarding these larger knowledge classes—either manually or by exploring the collection visualization (see section 3).

Fig. 3. First prototype for the digital edition of the Bibliotheca Eugeniana’s handwritten catalog.

By combining data generated by HTR of the handwritten catalog, by machine learning on the supralibros bindings, and from the modern library catalog (catalog entries, full-texts), we are building a digital edition (see figure 3 for a first prototype), which can serve as a resource for future research on the Bibliotheca Eugeniana. In addition, the emerging database can be used to visualize this historic book collection—for analytical and exploratory purposes.

3 Visualizing the Bibliotheca Eugeniana

Visualizations of cultural collections, such as the Bibliotheca Eugeniana, do not focus on search or close reading, as digital editions mainly do, but on generating new opportunities for open exploration, collection analysis and comprehension [23]. They foster serendipitous knowledge discovery [20] and they also grant access for users without prior knowledge of a collection’s content [14]. As such, they have been called *generous interfaces* [21] to emphasize the removal of barriers and the provision of multiple collection overviews, which actively encourage user interaction, such as browsing, exploring, and (scalable) reading.

For the design of such visualizations, three factors are known to provide valuable guidance [17]: (1) the intended user group, (2) the data, and (3) the

specific tasks or user activities, which should be made possible with the interface. In our case, the *user group* is twofold: On the one hand, analyses by experts (literary and history scholars, librarians) should be supported; on the other hand, we aim to increase awareness of and knowledge about the collection by the general public. The design of productive collection visualizations is often based on user-centered co-design approaches [5], where representatives of the relevant target groups are involved in design workshops and evaluation sessions[15]. As such, we conducted regular workshops with experts of the Bibliotheca Eugenia, which helped to understand the requirements and needs of the target users and to develop and refine a prototypical visualization-based interface.

Regarding *data*, we combine most of the available information described earlier (see table 1 for an overview)¹⁰. For the visualization, we firstly focused on data dimensions which helped to aggregate and demarcate the books of the historical collection from other books in the library hall and to show patterns within: Temporal and geographic origins, different classifications, location within the library hall, language, supralibros type, and binding color. An important factor for the design of visualizations is the data’s completeness (e.g., as it is difficult to place books without location on a map) and uncertainty (e.g. non-standardized place names are often ambiguous).¹¹

Table 1. Overview of the Data Structure.

Data	Source	Completeness	Uncertainty
Title	HC, MC	high	low
Author	HC, MC	medium-high	low
Classification	HC	high	medium
Keywords (normed)	MC	medium-low	medium
Year of publication	HC, MC	medium-high	low
Place of publication	HC, MC	medium-high	low
Location within ONB	MC	high	low
Language (normed)	MC	medium-high	medium
Digitized book	ABO	medium-high	medium
Supralibros	ML	medium-low	very low
Binding color	ML	medium-low	low

Sources: HC—handwritten catalog, MC—modern catalog, ML—machine learning, ABO—Austrian Books online

¹⁰ At the time of submission the mapping between the handwritten and the modern catalog is still ongoing. Therefore, the first prototype does not take the data from the handwritten catalog into account. At the time of the conference, we will be able to present a more advanced version of the prototype and also report concrete numbers.

¹¹ We will not discuss the visualization of uncertain or missing data in this paper. For an overview on visualization strategies for uncertain data within collection visualizations see [24], for their discussion within our project, see [22].

Finally, concerning the users' *activities*, we aim to support the exploration of multiple aspects of the collection: Currently, the most important access point to the Bibliotheca Eugeniana is the State Hall¹², where most of the books are located and which also serves as an anchor point in the visualization (answering questions like: Which books within the State Hall are part of this collection? Are there specific arrangement principles?). Visualizations should unveil the general structure and composition of the Bibliotheca Eugeniana (Which knowledge classes are prevalent? Where do the books come from? Which languages are dominant? From which timeframe have books been collected?). Furthermore, the findings of the machine learning algorithm should be made accessible (Which supralibros have been found? Is there a relationship between binding color and the catalog's classification or the physical shelving?).

Fig. 4. Overview on the starting page of the tripartite visualization prototype: book list with search bar (left), bookshelves in the ONB's State Hall (center), and different configurable analytical views (right).

In line with our multimodal research approach and the idea of generous interfaces, multiple visualization views have been developed with regard to the collection and classification data in order to shed light on these questions. The first visualization prototype¹³ builds on all books from the modern catalog with a BE shelfmark, as well as the machine learning results, and features a tripartite layout (see figure 4). It consists of (1) a book list on the left, (2) an overview

¹² A virtual 3D tour of the State Hall is available here: <https://www.onb.ac.at/en/museums/state-hall/visit/virtual-state-hall>

¹³ The visualization prototype can be accessed under <https://demo.mindfactor.at/eugeniana/>.

of the books' arrangement in the State Hall in the center, and (3) a window to switch between multiple analytical views on the right. The three parts of the interface are coordinated [18], so that an interaction or selection within one view also influences what data are displayed in the other views.

The *book list* contains a color-coded list of book titles based on the current visualization selection. Next to the title for each book, it provides information on the year and place of publication, as well as on the author. For most titles, the digitized book can be inspected on demand to indulge in close reading. Below the book list, a search bar allows for keyword-based filtering of the booklist.

The *State Hall View* is at the center of this interface. It represents the twelve bookshelves in the oval-shaped center of the State Hall. Upon selection of a specific bookshelf, a close-up view of this shelf appears in the center where each book is shown as a small, color-coded bar (see figure 5). Upon hovering such a bar, the details of the selected book are displayed and the associated entry in the book list is highlighted.

Fig. 5. Detail view of one row in bookshelf BE.4 with one book highlighted on mouseover, color-coding based on the binding color.

The *analytical view* can be chosen by the users, based on their interests and needs. They can gain an overview of the sets of the machine learning results (enabling the user to filter, for example, only books with a supralibros binding or only yellow-bound books) in a bubble chart (see figure 4, right). Alternatively, they can explore the temporal origins of the books and inspect only manuscripts from a specific period in a time-based histogram (see figure 6, left). We also plan to include a taxonomy visualization of the historical Leibniz classification and a map of the places of publication based on the data from the handwritten catalog

(see figure 6, center and right). The treemap in the center currently shows only top-level knowledge categories, while subcategories have been omitted to reduce information density. However, they can be displayed on demand and thereby allow for multiple levels of exploration.

Fig. 6. Three different analytical views (from left to right): timeline histogram, treemap of the handwritten catalog’s knowledge classification, and map view with places of publication.

Across all three parts of the interface, two different variants of *color-coding* are available, based on the Machine Learning results. One focuses on the question whether a book has been part of the Bibliotheca Eugeniana (see figure 4): Certain (in red) includes all books where we found Eugene’s coat of arms on the leather binding; Uncertain (in orange) includes books within the time range of Eugene’s collecting activities, where no coat of arms was found or safely identified (i.e., which could be part of his collection, but we do not know for sure yet); Definitely not (in gray) comprises books which have been published after Eugene’s death, and therefore cannot be part of his collection. The second coloring option is based on the bindings’ identified colors.

To serve experts as well as non-experts, we decided on a configurable approach, which starts from the simplest possible view: a book list, the bookshelves in the State Hall, and three bubbles with their association to the Bibliotheca Eugeniana, as depicted in figure 4. From there, users can start to explore the collection interactively and incrementally add complexity with further analytical views. For novel users, we added a tutorial with background information and instructions. Complementing this exploratory interface, we also aim to utilize techniques of visualization-based storytelling [12] to raise awareness of the existence and relevance of the collection among the general public. The interface will be available for exploring the collection in digital space as well as for digitally extending a visit to the State Hall with in-depth insights into the history and structure of this unique collection.

In four focus groups, we asked a diverse group of 15 experts (from history to library sciences and marketing) to evaluate the interface from the perspective of historians, librarians, tourists or students. The feedback was used to improve the interface and to develop narratives for storytelling. Overall, the feedback was very positive and all groups reported that they could gain novel insights into the book collection based on the visualizations. For students, it "makes history accessible" by showing topics of relevance in European baroque. For tourists, it can expand visits of the State Hall by making the books in the shelves more tangible. The historians observed that the interface offers "multiple access points for exploration and directed search". They generated novel hypotheses for further research and also expressed their interest to re-use the machine learning algorithms on other book collections. For the librarians the interface triggered an intense discussion on the ordering principles within the State Hall - and how they changed over time.

4 Discussion

Already in 1739, there was regret about the lack of a printed catalog for the *Bibliotheca Eugeniana* which could have fostered wider access¹⁴. These limitations prevailed until the beginning of the 21st century, when accessing its catalog and finding objects was still perceived to be quite cumbersome [6]. The project *Bibliotheca Eugeniana Digital* closes the accessibility gap for this library with a digital edition for experts and a visualization-based interface for everyone. To do so, it interweaves different disciplinary approaches and methods from the fields of collection studies, library and information studies, data science, information visualization, and digital scholarly editing. With its focus on digital methodologies, the project also aims to demonstrate and evaluate, what recent technologies can contribute to the reconstruction of historical book collections¹⁵.

Reconstructing historical book collections is a common research topic in the humanities. Traditionally, this type of work relies on the time-consuming practice of manual inspection and on the harvesting of catalogs, bibliographies, and archival resources (e.g. [11]). Digitization options for books and catalogs, as well as algorithmic tools for harvesting and mapping bibliographic data from these sources, have significantly improved the efficiency of such research endeavors [8]. The project *Bibliotheca Eugeniana Digital* went one step further by using machine learning algorithms at several steps for the reconstruction and analysis of the targeted collection: the identification of provenance features (supralibros bindings) in a vast corpus of digitized books (Austrian Books Online) by means of machine-learning-based classification of image features, the transcription of a handwritten catalog by using a machine-learning-based model for Handwritten

¹⁴ "Bey diesen allen ist aber zu bedauern, daß kein Catalogus von dieser Bibliothec heraus gekommen." [1, p.1137]

¹⁵ The machine learning algorithms, resulting data sets, and source codes will be published for re-use by the scientific community at the end of the project in October 2024.

Text Recognition, and the automatic matching to titles in ONB’s modern digital catalog. All these data sources are integrated within a digital edition, which now provides instant search-based access to Prince Eugene’s library for research purposes.

To balance out the well-known limitations of search-centered interfaces, we are augmenting the digital edition with a visualization-based interface to promote the collection’s digital generosity and openness—not only for non-expert users. Among the core strengths of collection visualizations is their ability to flatten access barriers and to introduce novel pathways for their active exploration, analysis, and communication. Mitchell Whitelaw has made the case for such amendments: “As an interface, search fails to match the ample abundance of our digital collections and the generous ethos of the institutions that hold them. A more generous interface would do more to represent the scale and richness of its collection. It would open the doors, tear down the drab lobby [where a search slot blocks the way]; instead of demanding a query it would offer multiple ways in, and support exploration as well as the focused enquiry where search excels. In revealing the complexity of digital collections, a generous interface would also enrich interpretation by revealing relationships and structures within a collection.” [21, para 3]

In line with these reflections, the project Bibliotheca Eugeniiana Digital aims to deliberately go beyond search slots and result lists and offers multiple avenues for visual exploration in addition. It is the future evaluation and documentation of the added benefits—together with possible drawbacks—which we consider to be of wider relevance to the field of library studies. While visualization-based interface designs are gaining ground for cultural collections in general [23], related insights and lessons for library visualizations—especially for historical book collections—are still rather limited. With this project, we hope to collect evidence for the value and relevance of this strategy in this particular field, and to encourage other library projects to follow the path ‘beyond search’. It stands to reason, that only such amendments can recreate the natural pathways to situated sensemaking and serendipitous knowledge discovery, which have always fascinated the visitors of physical library spaces, but which are frequently cut off by the standard interfaces to contemporary digital knowledge environments [4].

With a digital edition and a collection visualization, the project Bibliotheca Eugeniiana Digital also developed a digital knowledge base to facilitate future research into the library. For example, the current work makes it possible to analyze the assumed [16], but also questioned [13] correlation of binding colors and knowledge classification empirically. It can help to understand the current extent of the book collection and its whereabouts within the ONB. It sheds light on the actual arrangement principles on the bookshelves in the State Hall—and it could even foster the creation of hypotheses about the collection’s original arrangement in Eugene’s palace. As such, the project is strengthening and consolidating the basis for future research on object and collection level. It can help to unveil and identify specific literary treasures that lie within this historic book

collection, but it also paves the way for a corpus-based assessment and interpretation of knowledge collection and classification strategies in the Baroque era. In line with the concept of scalable reading, it sharpens the view on the metaphorical forest and its trees, providing answers and generating questions for novel lines of inquiry.

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